

ISic0124

I.Sicily inscription 0124

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Baldassare Romano, inventory 30ae

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Africanus

2. ave · et · vale

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

Africanus. Hello and goodbye.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285288

EDR 127509

EDCS 10900639

Bibliography

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese.

Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica. Palermo / Rome. At 43
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